

I.FAST

Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology

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MILESTONE REPORT

INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP TO DEFINE R&D PLANS

MILESTONE: MS16

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ABSTRACT

The MUon Collider Strategy network (MUST) considers the development of an optimized R&D roadmap towards a future facility as a mandatory step forward, identified as the I.FAST milestone MS16. The International Muon Collider Collaboration IMCC, established with the goal of a Design Study, urge to define a feasible R&D plan as well. Embedded in the IMCC and MuCol Annual Meeting at CERN on March 12-15 2024, parallel sessions were dedicated to discuss and identify challenges, issues and steps forward in each area of the machine and experiment R&D. Those sessions were identified as the International workshop to define R&D plans. Key elements for R&D planning and separate timeline were summarized in the plenary final session.

I.FAST Consortium, 2025

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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Executive summary

The Design Study of a Muon Collider at center of mass energy of the order of 10 TeV presents several technological challenges which demand for a robust R&D plan on crucial enabling technologies. The constraints on the experiment design and physics potential are mainly due to the Beam Induced Background shaped by the Machine Detector Interface derived by the new lattice at 10 TeV. To maximize the physics potential, the machine performance and luminosity optimization define the key elements for the R&D plan. The muon production from an intense proton beam requires an high-power target embedded in a high solenoidal magnetic field. To produce intense muon beams an efficient and fast cooling system is mandatory. Dedicated studies for a feasible design and integration of an elementary cooling cell exploiting normal conductive RF embedded into innovative HTS solenoidal field technologies including absorbers are on-going. The fast acceleration and collider rings require the development of dedicated RF and magnet systems. A muon ionizing cooling demonstrator design and a possible first implementation plan on CERN site is a primary goal of the International Muon Collider collaboration towards the next European Strategy of Particle Physics update.

1 Introduction

As a consequence of the 2020 European Strategy for Particle Physics Update [1], a Bright Muons Beam panel contributed to prepare the Accelerator R&D Roadmap [2]. A comprehensive R&D program was presented and approved by CERN Council to finalize the design study of a multi-TeV facility able to reach the 10 TeV and higher energy in the center of mass with adequate instantaneous luminosity to guarantee the physics potential exploitation of this unique machine proposed for the post HL-LHC era.

The third Annual Meeting of the International Muon Collider Collaboration held at CERN in person (also reachable from remote) on March 12-15 2024 fulfilled the milestone M16. It was indeed also conceived to specifically address the status of technical feasibility, the issues identified in initial phase of the study, the first projections of the required R&D, and the plan for dedicated test facilities and a muon cooling demonstrator.

The meeting covered all areas of study and development, focusing on:

- (i) the result of the first iteration on the muon collider parameters, as far as physics, detectors, accelerator performance and technology are concerned, including considerations on staging;
- (ii) the status of technical feasibility, the issues that have been identified in this initial phase of the study, first projections of the required R&D, and the plan for dedicated test facilities and a muon cooling demonstrator;
- (iii) the advance of work with respect to the IMCC and MuCol programme and milestones.

As for our previous meetings, we wish to profit from this opportunity to strengthen integration among the various activities and encourage the growth of the collaboration. Special attention was devoted to the outcome of the US P5 process, and its implications for future activities.

The first phase of the R&D programme should be the completion of a start-to-end facility design. It also includes hardware development of components that drive the overall timeline for the collider such as the superconducting magnets and the muon cooling technology, with the first cooling cell integration prototyping. The machine detector interface studies also play a significant role defining the constraints on the shielding structure to be inserted into the detector volume and the choice of technologies to optimize performances, including the integration of the detector magnet.

2 Development of the R&D programme

The proposed R&D plan aims to achieve:

- the development of the detector volume design including the detector magnet to optimise the performance and minimise the impact of beam induced background with the final design of the machine detector interface, with the dedicated shielding structure;
- the muon cooling technology demonstration programme to fully develop this novel technology with the essential components: high field HTS solenoids, normal conductive cavities and absorbers. Test of a full cooling cell with RF power will allow verification of the integrated performance. The demonstrator facility will test several types of cooling cells with beam to demonstrate the technology;
- an intense programme to establish the superconducting magnet performance through the construction and test of models and prototypes. It will focus in particular on HTS solenoids for the muon production target and the muon cooling. These have strong synergy with applications in society such as fusion reactors. A model of the collider ring dipoles will also be constructed and establish the field at large aperture;
- a start-to-end model of the collider: the completion of the lattice design along the whole complex and its optimisation will guide the components' design. The development of simulation tools that include the relevant beam physics, such as collective effects and imperfections as well as the relevant mitigation techniques, will enable robust luminosity predictions. A study of the machine availability will establish the integrated luminosity performance and guide component and accelerator design;
- experimental tests in combination with further design work will verify the target robustness;
- conceptual designs of the superconducting and normal-conducting cavities along the whole complex. Experimental verification of the performance limits will allow to optimise the complex design. In particular, the construction of an infrastructure to test RF in a high magnet field will enable experimental optimisation and verification of the normal-conducting muon cooling RF;
- the development of high-power, high-efficiency klystrons to be instrumental for the muon cooling cell test and enable cost effective design;
- the studies of the performance of the fast-ramping magnet systems and power converter for the Rapid- Cycling Synchrotrons (RCS) to be demonstrated;
- the site and environmental impact studies, including civil engineering, which will allow optimisation for power consumption and material usage as well as minimising the impact of the machine for the local environment;
- an overall optimisation of the complex for cost, power consumption and risks to be carefully performed and particularly essential since we cannot base ourselves on experience with previous similar projects. This optimisation will also cross the boundaries between the different systems.

The Muon Cooling demonstrator must meet the following key challenges:

- create a muon beam with a sufficiently high flux of particles in the small transverse and longitudinal acceptance of the cooling system;
- operate a cooling system, including integrated RF cavities, solenoids and magnets, in a day-to-day manner;
- commission and operate the system to transmit beam through the lattice and cool it;
- measure the beam before and after cooling to characterise the beam and demonstrate successful emittance reduction to evaluate the performance.

The talks during the workshop cover most of the topics above reported creating a timeline and a roadmap of the actions to do. Hereinafter a brief summary is reported.

2.1 MACHINE DETECTOR INTERFACE

Due to the short lifetime and decay of muons, the machine-detector interface (MDI) in a muon collider presents unique challenges to be addressed by a dedicated inclusive shielding and detector design. The MDI is the crucial area where the final focusing magnets and the detector are integrated, designed to minimize background radiation from muon decays while maximizing the detection of collision events. A shielding system, protruding into the detector is mandatory and several studies on the shapes and material are on-going. A key role in the studies is played by the effort to mitigate all the different effects of beam-induced background. The primary contribution to this background has been identified as decay products of the muon beams and by the coherent pair production at higher energy. If not properly managed, these decays arriving at the detector could limit its performance. Several configurations at 3 and 10 TeV were presented and physics results showed the feasibility of the present design.

2.2 MUON PRODUCTION

The muon collider design presents significant challenges, particularly in the target area due to the intense radiation and heat generated by the proton beam. The International Muon Collider Collaboration is actively studying various target materials and technologies to optimize muon production while mitigating these challenges. The target system design is complex, requiring a 20 T solenoidal field to focus the produced beam.

The proton collisions create pions, which then decay into muons. These muons are then captured, cooled, and accelerated to the desired energy for collisions in the collider.

Several options are under discussions on target materials and the classical solution would be to use a graphite target. Alternative solutions consider the use of fluidized tungsten bed as possible target material or a liquid Pb target.

2.3 MUON COOLING

The muon cooling is essential because muons are produced with a large momentum spread and emittance. Ionization cooling is the unique technique that could be used to reduce the muon beam's emittance.

In such technique, muons pass through a low Z material, losing energy primarily through ionization of the material's atoms and then reducing the muon's momentum.

After cooling, the longitudinal momentum is then restored using RF cavities. The beam crosses several cooling cell before finally the beam could be injected into the next stem of the facility.

2.4 THE COOLING CELL DESIGN

A cooling cell is the basic element of the muon cooling line to reduce the transverse emittance of the muon beam. The muons generated by the collision of a proton beam with the production target have a large angular spread and a large momentum spread. The capture and cooling section will maximize the number of particles captured, and reduce their transverse momentum through interactions with a low-Z material, which will reduce both the longitudinal and the transverse momentum. A Radio-Frequency (RF) cavity will re-accelerate the particles to restore their longitudinal momentum. Through this, the beam is cooled, meaning the particles decrease their transverse energy and their energy spread with respect to the reference energy. Strong superconducting solenoids are present throughout the beam trajectory to maintain its focus around the reference trajectory, limiting the transverse beam size.

The cooling performance is critical for the luminosity of the collider, which is one of the key performance indicators of the whole machine.

A preliminary layout of the cooling cell is shown in Figure 1 and the dedicated discussions addressed the different parameters required to optimize the final performances. Moreover dedicated integration studies are on-going to allow the collaboration to plan for initial laboratory tests, to be followed by more complex beam tests.

Fig. 1 Schematic of a Cooling Cell with reference parameters for RF, Magnets and absorber.

2.5 DEMONSTRATOR

The muon cooling demonstrator is proposed to demonstrate the key components of a full muon cooling channel. It will represent the first muon ionizing cooling facility able to fully apply to all six phase-space dimensions, chaining multiple cooling cells of different parameters to be finalized both in design and components integration. The parameters of the muon cooling demonstrator are described in table 1.

The Demonstrator must meet the following key challenges:

- create a muon beam with a sufficiently high flux of particles in the small transverse and longitudinal acceptance of the cooling system;
- operate a cooling system, including integrated RF cavities, solenoids and absorber in a day-to-day manner;
- commission and operate the system to transmit beam through the lattice and cool it;
- measure the beam before and after cooling to characterise the beam and demonstrate successful emittance reduction.

Cooling System	
Parameter	Value
Cell length	2 m
Peak solenoid field on-axis	7.2 T
Dipole field	0.2 T
Dipole length	0.1 m
RF real estate gradient	22 MV/m
RF nominal phase	20°
RF frequency	704 MHz
LiH wedge thickness on-axis	0.0342 m
LiH wedge apex angle	5°
LH2 wedge thickness on-axis	0.19 m
LH2 wedge apex angle	30°

Table 1: Preliminary hardware parameters for the Demonstrator: with both a lithium hydride (LiH) and liquid hydrogen (LH2) absorber.

2.5.1 Site for a demonstrator at CERN

Two potential sites have been identified so far on the CERN estate that can host the demonstrator, the TT10 and the TT7 tunnels. The first site would be suitable for a high power (>2 MW) target but would require extensive new civil engineering. The second site would be suitable only for a low (10 kW) power target but would largely reuse existing tunnels. The low power site would have no limitation in terms of maximum instantaneous intensity; the limitation would be on the average current. This site is therefore fully suitable for studies of cooling efficiency, but it would require more time to build large statistical samples.

The high power site is placed to receive beam from the transfer line from the PS to the SPS and could potentially receive the entire 80 kW of beam available from the PS, and could, in future be connected to the High Power SPL as designed in [1].

Work has begun towards a beam physics design for the target region and transport line that will be used to bring muons into the cooling system.

3 Future plans

Three main R&D areas have been identified to be on the critical path and therefore define the technically limited timeline:

- The muon cooling complex and its technology: development of muon cooling modules is essential in order to integrate superconducting solenoids, normal-conducting RF, robust absorbers and auxiliary structures in a tight space and to verify mechanical robustness of the modules. Integration of several modules into a facility with beam will ensure convincing demonstration of this novel technology.
- The superconducting magnet technology: development of HTS-based solenoids for the target/captures systems and the muon cooling channel are essential for production of quality muon beams. The superconducting accelerator magnets in the collider ring define luminosity performance of the machine and requires dedicated shielding structures to avoid quenching induced by muons decay.
- The two detectors and related technologies (including detector magnet) and infrastructures: development of the detector and magnet technologies and design reconstruction tools necessary to suppress the beam induced background are essential for ensuring that physics goals of the machine are met.

The scope and the timeline of the R&D program necessary to finalize the on-going design studies and to establish the feasibility of critical technological components are one of the major effort of the IMCC collaboration to be presented as input to the 2026 Update to the European Strategy of Particle Physics.

References

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